

NEED TO FORM CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN EDUCATORS

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ABSTRACT

The article presents ideas about the need to develop creative competence in pedagogues.

Key words: professional creativity.

The main methodological and conceptual approaches to the development of personal creativity qualities, psychological features of the formation of individual qualities of a creative person, issues related to the technologies of organizing the professional creativity of pedagogues in the continuous education system are covered. Cognitive activity is a multifaceted, complex process, and its effectiveness in the implementation of education depends on the pedagogue's ability, inquisitiveness, thinking, observation and creative approach. That is why creativity occupies an important place in the process of learning.

Creativity represents the implementation of research tasks, such as the analysis of new ideas unknown in science and practice, the study, development, testing and comparison of various new technical and creative solutions. This process is important because it increases and strengthens the level of knowledge of the pedagogue, and serves to significantly increase the qualities of active and independent thinking, spiritual and educational level, and to become a real creative person in the future. Creativity is important as it serves to ensure the strength and perfection of the knowledge acquired by pedagogues, to form active and independent thinking personality traits in them, and to develop their intellectual abilities. This situation is of great importance in mastering the fundamentals of science of future specialists, in the implementation of direct leadership of this process, in the introduction of approaches

based on professional creativity. Creativity is considered the most basic and active form of manifestation of independent thinking qualities in a person, and it can be classified according to the following signs: type of creativity (technical, technological, organizational, economic, social, spiritual, pedagogical, didactic, professional, mixed) ; creativity level (mono creativity, multi creativity, mega creativity); scope of work (specialization, specialty, field of knowledge, inter-branch, national, regional, inter-regional, international); duration of creation (short-term, medium-term, long-term); form of creativity (innovative, research, educational, investment, mixed); according to their general aspects (implementation of new ideas; promotion of new solutions in principle; practical application of innovation); according to the meaning and complexity of the created creative product (rationalization proposal; invention; discovery). [1, 102]

Pedagoglar ijodkorlik faoliyatini tashkil qilish mustaqil fikrlashni rivojlantirish, bilim egallashdagi intiluvchanlik, ilmiy dunyoqarashni shakllantirish, o'zlashtirilgan bilimlarni ta'lim va amaliy faoliyatda mustaqil qo'llay olishga o'rgatishda namoyon bo'ladi.

Within the framework of the conducted research, the concepts of creativity, knowledge, skills, and abilities specific to the personality of the pedagogue were clarified from the research point of view. Including: knowledge of creativity - a systematic reflection in the human mind as a product of cognitive activity of concepts and imaginations required for the development of a new solution; creativity skills - determines the level of quick and complete implementation of mental process stages in goal-oriented creative activity. Creativity skills mean the level of a person's ability to perform the reproductive stages of creative activity in a partially automated manner, while understanding only the first stages of the mental process. [5, 28]

In order to develop knowledge, skills and abilities of creativity, pedagogues need to systematically use creative educational tasks, problem situations and exercises aimed at developing spatial imagination during training. Factors for the development of creativity of pedagogues should be the basis of educational activities in every subject and every lesson. Creative activity covers all aspects of the teacher's and pedagogue's activity, serves to organize it effectively and ensure the quality of the educational process.

Working with scientific and technical information plays an important role in the development of creative activity of pedagogues. Various newsletters, dictionaries and glossaries, regulatory and legal documents on scientific activity, inventiveness and patent science materials serve as an important resource for pedagogues. Creative pedagogical technologies are considered to be an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of creative activities of pedagogues in determining the stages of

developing problem thinking, collecting data and checking the results, assuming that pedagogues perform productive activities in solving the assigned tasks. We have defined the concept of creative pedagogical technology as a methodical system of developing the professional creativity of pedagogues, which provides the purposeful implementation of the programmed tasks and the content and processes of the composition of the professional qualities of the individual.

The introduction of creative pedagogical technologies is carried out on the basis of the following approaches:

1. Research approach based on practical knowledge. Within this approach, creative pedagogical technologies of organization and development of professional creativity of pedagogues are characterized by gathering new practical information.

2. Research approach based on theoretical knowledge. In this approach, the main attention is focused on the search for new theoretical knowledge and fields of knowledge about the professional creativity of pedagogues.

In evaluating the effectiveness of the pedagogical system of ensuring the integrity of the professional creativity of teachers, we based on the three-component model of cognitive processes embodying learning, intelligence and creativity. According to this, any cognitive process should embody the acquisition, application and modification of cognitive experience. That is, it is possible to explain the ability to absorb experience with learning, the efficiency of practical application of experience with general intelligence, and its change with creativity. When making a creative decision regarding the solution of problematic educational tasks, the processes related to understanding its essence, creating projects that serve as a solution, and choosing the most optimal of them are in a mutually demanding sequence of cognitive, divergent and convergent thinking. will be done.

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